

Forcing and symmetry

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Abstract

Topological vector spaces (*TVS*) may analogues of set-theoretic forcing notions. These allow for some surprisingly profound symmetries in the constructible case. Here, we explore uniform and symmetric topological spaces which exhibit these symmetries.

1 Introduction

Let $\mathcal{R}$ be a ring with identity. Let $\mathcal{T}$ be a topological space. Define a stable bicategory $\mathcal{C}_2$ whose objects are pairs (r, k) , where r is an element of $\mathcal{R}$ and k is a tuple consisting of local coordinates over $\mathcal{T}$.

Since the category of rings is presentable, a ring $\mathcal{R}$ is manifestly a set; ergo, the notion of forcing is applicable. For a ring $\mathcal{R}$, a forcing notion is an injection $\mathcal{R} \xrightarrow{\aleph} \mathcal{R}^+ \cong \mathcal{R} \Vdash \mathcal{R}^+$ into an overring induced by the map $\aleph$. However, it is not exactly clear what the appropriate forcing notion for a topological space is. A good hunch is that, for a topological space $\mathcal{T}$, endowed with the Euclidean topology, the map $\mathcal{T}^n \xrightarrow{q} \mathcal{T}^m$ is isomorphic to an immersion of a space of dimension n into one of dimension $m > n$, with a fiber of codimension q .

Combining these two notions, we obtain a refinement of naked forcing; let us call this notion *symmetric forcing*. This is described by the functor

$$\mathfrak{Walls} : A \xrightarrow{\Vdash} B \quad B = A \bigsqcup_i \beta_i$$

where $\beta_{\min(i)} \triangleright A^\circ$, and A° is the group completion of A .

Suppose we are given an overcategory $\mathcal{C}_2^+ \supset \mathcal{C}_2$, such that $((\mathcal{C}^+, \mathcal{C}) / \Vdash) = [\aleph]$. Then, we effectively have an exit path

$$\mathcal{E}\mathcal{P}_\aleph : SC \longrightarrow FC$$

from the category of second-countable spaces to the category of first countable spaces.

Axiom 1.1. *The above map is weight-preserving; i.e., the minimal cardinality for a base in $\mathcal{T}^n$ is the same in its image.*

We impose the above axiom so that the coarseness/granularity of the space is preserved across the forcing. This ensures that all of the internal homs remain intact.

Definition 1.1. *A symmetric topological space, $\mathcal{T}_{Sym}$, is a (separable) homogenous topological space $\mathcal{T}^d$ whose pointwise reflection $\Sigma(\mathcal{T}_*)$ has parameterization $\wp$ if and only if the representative point $*$ $\in \mathcal{T}$ has parameterization $\wp$.*

Let Sm/k denote the category of smooth, separable schemes of finite type over $Spec(k)$. Denote the class of maps $Sm/k \mapsto (\mathcal{C}_2)$ by $\underline{Hom}_k$. We want to consider the subclass of split maps $\underline{Hom}_k \rightrightarrows \underline{Hom}_{k,k}$ consisting of morphisms of finite type to the birational geometric representation of $\underline{Hom}_k$.

Proposition 1.1. *$\underline{Hom}_{k,k}$ is homeomorphic to $\Sigma(\mathcal{T}_*)$.*

Proof. We have $\Sigma(\mathcal{T}_*) : * \in \mathcal{T} \longrightarrow \dot{*} \in \dot{\mathcal{T}} \cong Cr_* \cong Cr_{\dot{k}} \cong \{\} \mapsto Id_{\dot{e}}$, thus giving us the desired homeomorphism. $\square$

Let $\overset{\Gamma}{\nabla}(k, d) = \gamma_{\nabla}$ be a generalized connection¹ $p \xrightarrow{\gamma_{\nabla}} q$. Let $\mathcal{T}_{Disc}$ be a discrete topological space. Then:

Axiom 1.2. *Every $\gamma_{\nabla} \in \mathcal{T}_{Disc}$ is an exit path.*

It suffices to show that γ_{∇} is the creation map on q , and that every discrete topological space is stratified. Thus, $\mathcal{T}_{Disc} \cong Strat_{\mathcal{T}}^*$, and every full fibration (i.e., non-quasi fibration) is an exit path $\mathcal{EP}_{pq} : p \mapsto \dot{p} \cong q$. Note that $\mathcal{T}_{Disc}$ is not a totally contractible space; thus, it is ≥ -2 -truncated.

Denote by $C(\mathcal{T}_{Disc})$ the smallest category containing every $(p, q) \in \mathcal{T}_{Disc}$. This is the minimal contraction of a disconnected topological space.

Proposition 1.2. *If $C(\mathcal{T}_{Disc})$ is symmetric, then every exit path it contains is a forcing notion $\mathcal{EP} \Vdash (p, q)$.*

Proof. Suppose $\mathcal{T}_{Disc} \cong Rep(\mathbb{Q})$. Then, given a smooth path γ_{∇} of length ℓ . Then, we have $(exp(\ell))^{-k}$ for all C^k . Thus, these values are transcendental over $\mathcal{T}_{Disc}$, and they force a new space, $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}_{Disc}$, such that p lies in the first and q lies in the second. $\square$

Remark 1.1. *In the above, the extension $\mathbb{Q} \cup [\mathbb{K}]$ is the Cauchy co-completion of $\mathbb{Q}$, sending every $x \in Rep(\mathbb{Q})$ to a uniform space $\mathcal{U}_x$. Uniform spaces are highly “symmetric” objects; they are necessarily complete, and for every such space $\mathcal{U}_{\bullet}$, there is a “main diagonal,” $\bullet \times \bullet \mapsto \Delta$. Further, these spaces are very amenable, as they may be translated into “topological vector spaces.”*

¹Preconnection

2 Constructible Symmetries

Let $T \rightrightarrows (s, t) \in T$ be a topological vector space sending every functor in $End(T)$ to a presentable pair. Then, there exists a main diagonal $\Delta \in T$ as described above.

Definition 2.1 (Constructibility). *We call a function $f(T)$ on T constructible if, for every germ $g \sim Diff_{(s,t)} \cong ([s, g, t]) / \simeq$, there is a sheaf O_g in T supporting the action of a flow coefficient on (s, t) .*

Paths can also be constructible. Consider a constructible exit path $\mathcal{EP}_{Const} : s \mapsto t$. This path consists of the following data:

1. A coequalizer $g \in [s, t]$ in $\underline{Hom}(s, t)$.
2. A map of sheaves $O_g \rightarrow O_g$ containing the class $[g]$ of germs.

When we are working with a real vector space, we always have $\Delta \subset \underline{Hom}(s, t)$ giving us at least one trivial symmetry: $(s, t) \rightarrow (\dot{s}, \dot{t})$ given by fixing a point as the origin and sending each point x to a point $\dot{x} = -(x, x)$.

Definition 2.2 (Compactness). *A subspace $S \subset T$ is said to be compact if, for all $x_i \in S$, the inverse limit $\lim_{0 \leftarrow i} x_i$ sends a point to itself.*

This gives us the trivial identity $Id_0 = Id_x \equiv Id_{x_0}$. We also have the identity $Id_{\dot{x}} = d(x, \dot{x}) = ((f(x) = 0) \sim \infty)$, sending each outcome of the distance function on a pair $(x, \dot{x})$ to a rational point at infinity, which is identified as the zero for a polynomial equation on x .

Lemma 2.1. *The above identities are constructible symmetric functors.*

We will call an identity function $Id_{x_i} : x_i \mapsto x$ local if $d(x, x_i) < \varepsilon$ for some small enough ε , and global otherwise.

Definition 2.3. *A local-to-global correspondence is a map $H_n(x_i) \mapsto H_{n+1}(x)$ which acts on the sheaf of germs of x , such that there is an induced forcing notion $x_i \Vdash (x \mapsto \dot{x} \in [x_i])$.*

We shall call the image of the above map a *mirror image* if it is etale.

Example 2.1. *Let $T \in \underline{Hom}(Top, Vec)$ be a topological vector space. Denote the class of open elements in each by $\mathfrak{o} \in Top$ and $\mathfrak{p} \in Vec$ respectively. The Koszul nerve $\mathcal{N}_{Kosz}^1 : \mathfrak{o} \rightleftarrows \mathfrak{p}$ defines the equivalence class $(Shv_{\mathfrak{o}, \mathfrak{p}}) / \simeq$, with every mirror image embedded into a constructible class. It suffices to show that the maps $\mathfrak{o} \mapsto \dot{\mathfrak{o}}$ and $\mathfrak{p} \mapsto \dot{\mathfrak{p}}$ send open kernels to open images, and thus the nerve is etale.*

Remark 2.1. *If a nerve of a constructible topological vector space is etale, then there will be a bijection between diffeomorphisms and opens:*

$$Diff_{T_{et}} \cong \Omega T$$

where $\Omega \equiv [\ell_*]$ is the subcategory of (based) loops in T .

2.1 Constructible modules

Let $\mathcal{N}_{Mod}$ be a module acting on a nerve. Let $\phi_{\mathcal{N}} : \mathcal{N}_{Mod} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}_{Mod}$ be a display map. We say the module is a *constructible module* if there is a loop group ΩG which supports the sheaf O_g as described above. By “supports,” we mean that the support of the class of flow functions $[f(x) \rightarrow \dot{x}]$ are supported on ΩG .

The map $\phi_{\mathcal{N}}$ can be thought of as a map of graphs, $\Gamma_{\mathcal{G}} \rightarrow \Gamma'_{\mathcal{G}}$, where $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}_x$ is the isotropy group of x . When, and only when, a mirror image exists for each x , then $\mathcal{G}$ is a groupoid. We have

$$\phi_{\mathcal{N}} \Vdash \mathcal{U}_x$$

for some uniform space $\mathcal{U}_x$. Complete² neighborhoods of $\mathcal{U}_x$ are called “entourages,” and are denoted by $\mathcal{E}$. The span of every $\mathcal{E}$ is written:

$$inf(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E}) \leftarrow \Delta \rightarrow sup(\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{E})$$

where the infimum is defined to be a quantity smaller than ε , and the supremum is equivalent to $\varepsilon \wedge \infty$. This forms a compass $\Omega_{<\varepsilon}^{\varepsilon \wedge \infty}$. Let us add the following fact:

Theorem 2.1. *Rep(Δ) is a symmetric topological space*

The proof of which the reader is left to verify.

3 Universals

Let $P(x)$ be a property of x . We shall call this property universal if it holds for every flat embedding $x^b \hookrightarrow \bullet$, and quasi-universal if it holds almost everywhere. Universality is always with respect, of course, to some Grothendieck universe $\mathcal{V}$.

Example 3.1. *A universal property for $\mathbb{N}$ is that for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \equiv_1 0$. That is to say, $n \bmod 1$ is equal to 0.*

Example 3.2. *A quasi-universal property for $\mathbb{R}$ is that r is nonzero $\forall r$.*

Put another way, a property is universal if, for a fiber spectrum x_b of x , and for every loop $\ell : x_b \rightarrow x_{b'}$, then $b = b'$. This leaves x invariant with respect to transport in some space of homotopy types. That is to say, for a spectral sequence containing x_b , its E_∞ page should resemble the n th page, for $n \ll \infty$.

Put yet another way, for some pair of evaluation maps $ev_0 : x_b \hookrightarrow x$ and $ev_1 : x_b \hookrightarrow x$, the canonical valuation $\mathfrak{o}(x)$ is the same in both.

Theorem 3.1. *It is the universal property of a symmetric topological space that the functor*

$$x \mapsto \dot{x}$$

has an inverse.

²Not necessarily co-complete

Example 3.3. *Given a foliation $\mathcal{F}_x$, leaving x fixed, if every leaf is diffeotopic to any other, then each leaf has a universal property containing its elements. This is a symmetric universal property; every leaf is non-empty (i.e., there is a bijection of leaves of elements onto non-empty sets of propositions, or facts) becomes the dual.*

Let $P(x)$ be a proposition about x . We say $P(x)$ is an *analogy* if, for every $P \simeq P'$, there is a $P(x) \simeq P(x')$. We say that the items on either side of the isomorphism are “analogous.” An analogy is complete if it contains its own closure, or in other words if the group completion for $G \ni (x \vee x')$ is given by the analogy. For a complete analogy, we write $\bar{A}(P, P')$. In a complete analogy, every x' is given the same universal property as every x .